
151. The Hyades main sequence

A QUARTER OF A CENTURY ago (!), I used the recently finalised Hipparcos astrometry to make the first ‘space-age’ study of the Hyades, covering its distance, structure, dynamics, and age (Perryman et al., 1998).

Let me quote from our Introduction: *‘The considerable importance of the Hyades cluster in studies of Galactic structure, in the understanding of the chemical evolution of the Galaxy, and in the determination of the Population I distance scale, is well documented in the literature. The nearest moderately rich cluster, with some 300 possible members, a total mass of some 300 – 400 M_{\odot} , and an age of around 600–800 Myr, it has an extension in the sky of about 20°. Although uncertainty in the distances of individual members has limited the definition of the cluster’s main sequence, and thereby its helium content and corresponding evolutionary sequence, it has nevertheless been used as the basic observational material for several fundamental relationships in astrophysics, including the location of the main sequence in the Hertzsprung–Russell diagram and the mass–luminosity relationship, as well as forming the basis for the determination of luminosities of supergiants, OB stars, and peculiar stars in clusters.’*

From Hipparcos, we found 282 members (13 new). The well-defined main sequence (shown below) gave a He-abundance $Y = 0.26 \pm 0.02$, an age of 625 ± 50 Myr, and a centre-of-mass distance of 46.34 ± 0.27 pc.

I REVIEWED some of the early Gaia DR2 results on the Hyades cluster in essay #20. Most relevant to this essay, Lodieu et al. (2019) identified 1764 objects sharing the cluster’s mean proper motion, more than doubling the pre-Gaia census of around 800 members, including a handful of white dwarfs, and a dozen brown dwarfs.

From 381 objects within the cluster’s 9 pc tidal radius, they derived a mean distance of 47.03 ± 0.20 pc, and a mean space velocity of 46.38 ± 0.12 km s⁻¹. Two other studies detailed the remarkable tidal tails using the Gaia DR2 data (Meingast & Alves 2019; Röser et al. 2019).

The cluster age of 625 ± 50 Myr, derived from its main sequence and model isochrones which include convective overshooting (Perryman et al., 1998), has been largely confirmed by means of stellar binaries (Lebreton et al., 2001), the cooling age of its white dwarfs (Lodieu et al., 2019), and constrained by lithium depletion at the stellar/sub-stellar limit (Martín et al., 2018). Effects of rotation (Brandt & Huang, 2015), and enhanced convective overshooting (Mazzei & Pigatto 1988; Tremblay et al. 2012) leave open the possibility of a yet greater age.

THE MEAN METALLICITY has also been subject to debate, with pre-Gaia estimates lying in the slightly super-solar range $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = 0.05\text{--}0.14$ dex. Part of the problem is the degeneracy between $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, the He-to-metal enrichment, $\Delta Y/\Delta Z$, and the convective mixing length parameter, α_{ML} , with the latter also dependent on the part of the main sequence being modelled. Using the PISA evolution models, and estimates of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = 0.14\text{--}0.18$, and the Gaia DR2 photometry and parallaxes, Tognelli et al. (2021) obtained mean values of $\alpha_{\text{ML}} = 2.01 \pm 0.05$ and $\Delta Y/\Delta Z = 2.03 \pm 0.33$.

A KEY POINT TO emphasise is that ongoing improvements in the observational definition of the Hyades main sequence has led to improvements in stellar models, such as the effects of superadiabatic convection in the outer layers of partially convective stars (Castellani et al., 2001), and the incorporation of updated input physics, including opacities (Degl’Innocenti et al., 2008).

FURTHER ADVANCES in defining the Hertzsprung–Russell diagram of the Hyades cluster are becoming available from subsequent Gaia data releases, EDR3 in 2020 and DR3 in 2022, and a number of insights into state-of-the-art evolutionary models have followed.

Brandner et al. (2023b) used astrometry and photometry from Gaia EDR3 to construct a sample of *bona fide* single stars in the Hyades. The small observational uncertainties result in a tightly defined stellar sequence. The non-rotating MESA models (Choi et al., 2016) for $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = +0.25$, and an age of 710 Myr, provide a good fit for $M > 0.85M_{\odot}$, and for $M < 0.25M_{\odot}$. But for intermediate masses, the models systematically underpredict the observed luminosity. The figures below adopt an estimated age of 710 Myr, with the second showing the effects of varying the model’s assumed metallicity.

Brandner et al. (2023b) suggest that for (partially convective) stars with $M > 0.35M_{\odot}$, superadiabatic convection with α_{ML} following the solar model is unlikely to be optimal. For $M < 0.35M_{\odot}$, they suggest that the increased scatter in the stellar sequence might be due to the (unmodelled) ‘convective kissing instability’, an effect driven by variations in the ${}^3\text{He}$ energy production rate due to instabilities at the convective core–envelope boundary (van Saders & Pinsonneault, 2012).

For a Hyades-like stellar population, the application of solar-scaled models to sub-solar mass stars could, they conclude, result in a significant underestimate of the age, or to an overestimate of the metallicity. Meanwhile, do admire the quality of Gaia’s HR diagram!

Brandner et al. (2023b)

SIMILAR WORK on model fitting to the even ‘tighter’ main sequence based on the Gaia DR3 data was subsequently reported by Brandner et al. (2023a). To address the discrepancy between the observations and theoretical isochrones in the range $0.25 - 0.85M_{\odot}$, they based their updated models on the PARSEC code (PAдова and TRIeste Stellar Evolution Code), for which a revised temperature–Rosseland mean optical depth ($T - \tau$) relation was introduced by Chen et al. (2014).

The first figure below is their colour–magnitude diagram classified according to *bona fide* single main-sequence stars, probable binary and multiple systems, and stars with questionable photometry in at least one of the Gaia bands. The second shows the ~ 600 single-star candidates, and the best fitting PARSEC isochrones, with age 775 ± 20 Myr. While the fit is improved compared with MESA 1.2, over the colour range $B_p - R_p = 2.4 - 3.2$ mag ($\sim 0.22 - 0.40M_{\odot}$), stars are systematically brighter (or redder) than the isochrone predictions.

Brandner et al. (2023a)

FUTURE IMPROVEMENTS include accounting for rotation (mostly affecting the upper main sequence), more secure estimates of the He abundance (where the primordial abundance is imprinted in the lowest mass stars), eliminating still unidentified (more extreme) brightness- and mass-ratio binary systems, the effects of stellar activity and variability, and the possibility of ‘radius inflation’ identified in some of the Hyades stars, also from the Gaia data, by Jaehnicg et al. (2019).

The ongoing goal is, of course, to gain further insight into stellar structure, including as an improved probe of the ‘convective kissing instability’ region (van Saders & Pinsonneault 2012; Baraffe & Chabrier 2018; Mansfield & Kroupa 2021; Mansfield & Kroupa 2022).